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AYOLLARDA BOSH OG'RIG'I TERAPIYASINI TASHXISLASH VA OPTIMALLASHTIRISH BO'YICHA ZAMONAVIY QARASHLAR

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ANNOTANSIYA

Kuchlanish bosh og'rig'i birlamchi bosh og'rig'ining eng keng tarqalgan shakllaridan biri bo'lib, 30 daqiqadan bir necha kungacha davom etadigan og'riqli epizodlar bilan namoyon bo'ladi. Hayot davomida bosh og'rig'i tarqalishi 78% ni tashkil qiladi. Ayollar erkaklarinikiga qaraganda bir oz ko'proq azob chekishadi (A:E=5:4 nisbati). Bosh og'rig'i boshlanishining o'rtacha yoshi migrendan oshib ketadi va 25-30 yoshni tashkil qiladi. Bosh og'rig'ining turli shakllari yukini yaqinda tahlil qilish shuni ko'rsatdiki, bosh og'rig'i bilan bog'liq noto'g'ri ishlash darajasi va ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy zarar migrenga qaraganda ko'proq. O'choklilardan farqli o'laroq, bosh og'rig'ining kelib chiqishida genetik mexanizmlarning ishtirokini tasdiqlovchi ma'lumotlar olinmagan.

Kalit so'zlar: Bosh og'rig'i, ayollar, vash ko'rsatkichlari, McGill, EEG, TMS terapiyasi

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СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ВЗГЛЯДЫ НА ДИАГНОСТИКУ И ОПТИМИЗАЦИЮ ТЕРАПИИ ГОЛОВНОЙ БОЛИ У ЖЕНЩИН

АННОТАЦИЯ

Головная боль напряжения (ГБН) — одна из наиболее распространенных форм первичной головной боли (ГБ), проявляющаяся болевыми эпизодами продолжительностью от 30 мин до нескольких суток. Распространенность ГБН в течение жизни составляет 78%. Женщины страдают несколько чаще, чем мужчины (соотношение Ж:М=5:4). Средний возраст начала ГБН превышает таковой при мигрени и составляет 25–30 лет. Недавний анализ бремени различных форм ГБ показал, что степень дезадаптации и социально-экономический ущерб, связанные с ГБН, больше, чем при мигрени. В отличие от мигрени, данных, подтверждающих участие генетических механизмов в происхождении ГБН, не получено.

Ключевые слова: головная боль, женщины молодого возраста, показатели ваш, Мак-гилла, ЭЭГ, ТМС-терапия

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CURRENT VIEWS ON DIAGNOSIS AND OPTIMISATION OF HEADACHE THERAPY IN WOMEN

ANNOTATION

Tension headache (TTH) is one of the most common forms of primary headache (PH), manifested by pain episodes lasting from 30 min to several days. The lifetime prevalence of TTH is 78%. Women suffer slightly more often than men (ratio W:M=5:4). The average age of onset of TTH is higher than that of migraine and is 25-30 years. Recent analyses of the burden of different forms of TTH have shown that the degree of maladaptation and socioeconomic damage associated with TTH is greater than that of migraine. Unlike in migraine, there is no evidence to support the involvement of genetic mechanisms in the origin of TTH.

Keywords: headache, young women, your, Mc-guilla, EEG, TMS therapy

Introduction. Both peripheral and central nociceptive mechanisms are involved in the origin of TNN; the latter include sensitisation of trigeminal neurons, decreased pain thresholds and activity of the antinociceptive system, in particular, insufficiency of brainstem inhibitory mechanisms [4, 5]. Peripheral mechanisms are associated with the formation of dysfunction of pericranial muscles. Pain in TTH is associated with their painful tension (muscle spasm, or muscle-tonic syndrome). Peripheral factors are of greater importance in ETNN, while in CTTN - central factors associated with the development of sensitisation of pain structures. The formation of muscle-tonic syndrome (MTS) is based on the mechanism of "vicious circle", when repeated muscle tension arising in response to emotional stress leads to its reflex tension. As a result, the excitability of nociceptive neurons in the CNS structures, including motoneurons of the anterior horns of the spinal cord, increases. Prolonged tonic tension worsens blood supply to muscle tissue, leads to muscle hypoxia, acidosis and release of inflammatory mediators, which, in turn, bind to the corresponding receptors on the membrane of peripheral endings of muscle nociceptors, increase their sensitivity to pain (sensitisation). Loci of painful muscle thickening appear, which further increases the afferent flow of nociceptive impulses to the posterior horns of the spinal cord and other parts of the CNS. High levels of depression and anxiety, detected in most patients with TTH, facilitate pain transmission and contribute to the chronicity of the pain syndrome.

Risk factors and triggers

The main risk factors for TTH are "poor health" according to patients' self-assessment, inability to relax psychologically and muscularly, and insufficient sleep at night; the most frequent triggers are emotional stress (acute or chronic) and postural tension (prolonged head and neck in a forced uncomfortable position). With distraction or positive emotions, the pain may subside or disappear completely; with renewed emotional stress and/or muscular/positional tension, it may increase again. The main risk factors for the increase (chronicisation) of pain episodes of TTH include drug abuse (excessive use of analgesics) and psychiatric disorders, primarily depression, anxiety and somatoform disorders.

Diagnosis and clinical manifestations.

Diagnosis of TTH is made in accordance with the diagnostic criteria of ICTN-3 beta and is clinical, i.e. based on the analysis of complaints, history and normal neurological examination findings. Additional investigations are not indicated because they do not reveal changes specific to TTH. They are performed only if there are indications, the main of which is suspicion of symptomatic nature of cephalgia, i.e. doubt in probable clinical diagnosis of TTH. If the clinical picture is typical, after interviewing, examining the patient and analysing the compliance of clinical manifestations with the diagnostic criteria of ICHD-3 beta, the patient should be diagnosed with "Episodic TTH" or "Chronic TTH, and adequate treatment should be prescribed.

Clinical manifestations. Episodes of TH have duration from 30 min to several days, constant daily pain is possible. Headache, as a rule, diffuse, bilateral, involving the forehead, temples, parietal, occiput or the whole head; weak or moderate intensity (not more than 6-7 points on VASH), not pulsating, but compressive like "hoop" or "helmet". Pain does not increase with normal physical activity, accompanying symptoms are generally uncharacteristic, but mild nausea is possible, sometimes anorexia without nausea and vomiting; photophobia and phonophobia may also accompany TTH, but do not develop simultaneously, as in migraine.

Objective examination. As a rule, the neurological status of patients does not reveal organic disorders. During examination, signs of increased anxiety, hyperventilation, inability of the patient to psychological and muscular relaxation may be detected. Due to frequent complaints of tension and soreness of the neck and occipital muscles, an important part of the examination is the assessment of the state of the pericranial muscles. It has been shown that of the 3 diagnostic techniques (conventional palpation, EMG with surface electrodes, and algometry), the palpatory method is the most sensitive in the examination of pericranial muscles in patients with TTH and migraine [10]. Palpation should be performed with fine rotational movements with the second and third fingers while applying pressure in the area of

temporal, masseter, sternoclavicular-papillary, trapezius, as well as the posterior group of neck muscles (strap, inferior oblique). The diagnosis of "cervical muscle-tonic syndrome" or "pericranial muscle tension" is made in the presence of marked soreness up to the "jumping symptom" (the patient actively resists palpation due to muscle pain) in 2 or more muscle groups. If hypersensitivity (soreness) of the head and neck muscles is detected, a diagnosis of "ETTH with pericranial muscle tension" should be made. To determine the form of TTH, it is necessary to establish the number of days with TH per month. For this purpose, keeping a TN diary for at least 1 month is most informative. The TH diary also helps the patient and clinician to distinguish one type of TN from another (e.g. a migraine attack from an episode of TNN) and to establish the number of doses of painkillers taken to manage TN.

The patient should also be asked about the presence of comorbid disorders (CDs) that may further impair quality of life and require therapeutic management. Depression, anxiety disorders including panic attacks, somatoform and senesto-hypochondriac disorders, nocturnal sleep disorders, other pain syndromes including fibromyalgia are among the most common comorbid disorders in patients with TH Emotional and personality disorders maintain muscle tension and pain syndrome, lead to serious maladaptation and are one of the main factors in the chronicisation of TNN.

TTN and Drug Abuse. When patients with TTN abuse analgesics, we can talk about the presence of drug abuse, which is also a comorbid disorder. With significant abuse, drug-induced headache (LITN, or abusive headache) may form.

LITN is a complication of previous primary TN (migraine) but is a secondary form of cephalgia. In ICHD-3 beta, LITN is described in section 8.2, section 8, "TN associated with various substances or their withdrawal" and is subdivided into subtypes according to the drug(s) that caused the abuse ("culprit" drugs, or drugs of abuse).

LITN is characterised by the occurrence of headache for 15 or more days per month for more than 3 months, can develop with overuse of any TN medication (10 or 15 days per month or more depending on the type of "culprit" drug), and usually relieves after withdrawal. Potentially dangerous medications include: simple and combined analgesics, including non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), ergotamine derivatives, opioids; in migraine patients also specific drugs for the control of migraine attacks - triptans.

Clinical characteristics. The clinical picture of LITN resembles that of TTN and is manifested by almost daily dull pain in the whole head of a pressing or squeezing character of slight to moderate intensity. In contrast to TNN, the greatest intensity of pain is usually in the morning hours, and often TN wakes patients up, forcing them to take painkillers. Typical complaints are fatigue, drowsiness, decreased performance, difficulty concentrating, irritability, sleep disturbances; fear of pain may occur or worsen, forcing patients to take analgesics "in store".

Since drug abuse is one of the leading factors of chronicity of primary cephalgias, the addition of LITN significantly worsens the course of TNN, leading to an increase in the number of pain episodes up to the development of chronic TNN. The main risk group for the development of LITN is patients with the frequency of episodes of TTN 8-10 or more per month.

Diagnosis of LITN is clinical and is based on the analysis of the nature of TN, history (initial type of cephalgia) and data on the number and frequency of analgesic medications. The most important parameter is "the number of analgesic doses taken by the patient per month". The TN diary makes it much easier to obtain the necessary information. As there are no examination methods to confirm the diagnosis of LITN, referral for further investigations is not appropriate.

Even if TN does not fulfil all the criteria for LITN, it is important for both the physician and the patient to recognize that a drug abusive condition has been identified. Elimination of the abuse is a prerequisite for successful TTN prophylactic therapy: patients have been shown to respond poorly to prophylactic treatment until the abusive factor is identified and eliminated. Table 5 summarizes the diagnostic criteria for LITN.

Differential diagnosis of TTH

The differential diagnosis of TTN is most often made with mild migraine and TN associated with intracranial venous dysfunction [11]; in the presence of unilateral cephalgia, with cervicogenic TN. To facilitate the differential diagnosis, it is also advisable to keep a patient's TN diary.

In patients with CGD it is often necessary to carry out differential diagnostics with chronic migraine (CM), because the leading clinical manifestation of CM along with persisting frequent migraine attacks is the presence of TNN-like "background" pain. In this case, it is necessary to rely on the data of early history: in patients with HM, unlike CGDN, typical episodic migraine attacks and other features characteristic of migraine (hereditary history, typical triggers, relief of TN during pregnancy) are noted at the beginning of the disease. It is necessary to keep in mind the possible combination of TTH with other types of primary and secondary cephalgias: eTTN and migraine without aura, cTTN and cervicogenic TN, TTN and TN associated with BP elevation, sleep apnoea or temporomandibular joint dysfunction [1,8].

In the presence of drug abusers, differential diagnosis is often difficult. Most often it is necessary to differentiate LITN from CGD and CM. The presence of a history of typical episodic migraine attacks or TNS indicates the initial type of TN, and drug abuse over the past months or years suggests that the transformation of episodic TN into chronic TN has occurred under the influence of the abusive behaviour, and LITN is suspected. If the clinical picture fulfils the criteria for both TTN and LITN, 2 diagnoses should be made, for example: "Chronic TTN with pericranial muscle dysfunction. LITN associated with excessive intake of combined analgesics"[9].

Treatment

Treatment of TTN includes management of pain episodes and prophylactic treatment. Before selecting treatment tactics, behavioural therapy should be performed, which includes:

1. Explaining to the patient the benign nature of TTN and the mechanisms of its occurrence, dissuading the patient from believing that

there is an organic cause of TN. The main position: "TTN belongs to benign forms of headache, i.e. it is not associated with a disease of the brain, cerebral vessels or other organic disorders of the structures of the head and neck.

2 Justify the inappropriateness of additional investigations (except in cases of suspected symptomatic TNN).

3. Discussion of the role of risk factors for the development of TTN and provocateurs of pain episodes: the role of muscle tension during prolonged stay in a monotonous posture, emotional disorders (anxiety and depression), chronic emotional stress in the maintenance of pain syndrome and muscle tension, the need for training in psychological and muscle relaxation. Main point: "Avoidance of triggers of pain episodes, relaxation skills and lifestyle modification can significantly alleviate the course of TNN"[5].

4 Discuss risk factors for chronicity of TNN: explain the role of drug abusive behaviour, muscle tension, psychiatric and other comorbid disorders in increasing the frequency of episodes of TNN; patients with CGD who abuse analgesics should be educated about the need to avoid taking analgesics.

5. Clarification of treatment goals, mechanisms of action of prophylactic medications and the benefits of non-medication methods.

Based on the basic mechanisms of TTN formation, treatment should be comprehensive and aimed primarily at normalising the patient's emotional state and eliminating muscle tension, and if necessary, at correcting other comorbid disorders and drug abusers[2,7].

Conclusions: The choice of preventive treatment in LIGB depends on the initial form of cephalgia. For its specification it is necessary to carefully analyse anamnestic data at the beginning of the disease. After establishing the initial form of TN - "TTN", prophylactic therapy should be started simultaneously with the cancellation of the "guilty" drug and detoxification. The most effective in patients with TTN and LIGB is a course of amitriptyline (25-75 mg/day for 2-4 months). If ineffective, other antidepressants can be tried.

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PROBLEMS OF PRIMARY HYPOTHYROIDISM IN NEUROLOGICAL PRACTICE

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ANNOTATION

Among diseases of the endocrine system, hypothyroidism is the second most common after diabetes mellitus. The vast majority of hypothyroidism is primary, the causes of which are most often: surgical removal of part or all of the thyroid gland (thyroid gland), treatment with radioactive iodine or autoimmune thyroiditis (AIT). The incidence of primary hypothyroidism is about 4.6%. Subclinical hypothyroidism (SH) accounts for the majority at 4.3%, while 0.3% is manifest. Women tend to have the disease more often than men. The incidence of new cases of hypothyroidism among women is 3.5 cases per 1,000 people per year.

Keywords: thyroid gland, quality of life, cognitive dysfunction, primary hypothyroidism.

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ПРОБЛЕМЫ ПЕРВИЧНОГО ГИПОТИРЕОЗА В НЕВРОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ПРАКТИКЕ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Среди заболеваний эндокринной системы гипотиреоз является вторым по распространенности после сахарного диабета. При этом подавляющее большинство случаев гипотиреоза приходится на первичный, причинами которого чаще всего являются: оперативное удаление части или всей щитовидной железы (ЩЖ), лечение радиоактивным йодом или аутоиммунный тиреоидит (АИТ). Частота первичного гипотиреоза составляет около 4,6%. Большая часть при этом приходится на субклинический гипотиреоз (СГ) — 4,3%, а 0,3% — на манифестный. Женщины, как правило, болеют чаще мужчин. Частота новых случаев гипотиреоза среди женщин составляет 3,5 случая на 1000 человек в год.

Ключевые слова: щитовидная железа, качество жизни, когнитивная дисфункция, первичный гипотиреоз.

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NEUROLOGIK AMALIYOTDA BIRLAMCHI HIPOTIROIDIZM MUAMMOLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Endokrin tizim kasalliklari orasida hipotiroidizm diabetdan keyin ikkinchi o'rinda turadi. Shu bilan birga, hipotiroidizm holatlarining aksariyati birlamchi holatga to'g'ri keladi, buning sabablari ko'pincha: qalqonsimon bezning bir qismini yoki barchasini (qalqonsimon bez) jarrohlik yo'li bilan olib tashlash, radioaktiv yod bilan davolash yoki otoimmun tiroidit (ait). Birlamchi hipotiroidizm darajasi taxminan 4,6% ni tashkil qiladi. Ularning aksariyati subklinik hipotiroidizmga (SG) to'g'ri keladi — 4,3% va 0,3% — manifest. Ayollar erkaklarinikiga qaraganda tez-tez kasal bo'lishadi. Ayollarda hipotiroidizmning yangi holatlari yiliga 1000 kishiga 3,5 ta holatni tashkil qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: qalqonsimon bez, hayot sifati, kognitiv disfunktsiya, birlamchi hipotiroidizm.

Introduction: Currently, hypothyroidism (HT) is one of the most common forms of endocrine pathology. The prevalence of manifest hypothyroidism is 0.2 - 2%, subclinical - 10% [4,5]. The urgency of the problem of hypothyroidism in clinical practice of doctors of various specialities is due to the fact that thyroid hormone deficiency causes severe disorders in all organs and systems without exception. Polyorganic nature of the lesion includes the problems of thyroidology

in the sphere of interest of representatives of various disciplines. This fully applies to the influence of hypothyroidism on the mental and neurological status of patients [6,7].

The most studied in hypothyroidism in this respect are neuromuscular disorders (hypothyroid myopathy and myotonic phenomenon) and peripheral nerve damage, the prevalence of which is quite variable. Among the signs of organic brain damage, vestibulo-

ЖУРНАЛ НЕВРОЛОГИИ И НЕЙРОХИРУРГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

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